

ACTIVITY IS A SIGN OF PERSONAL SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT... (BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF THE WORKS OF ABDUL QADIR GILANI)

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Annotation: This article analyzes the fact that being busy or taking up a profession and being active in society is a sign of maturity as a sign of a person's spiritual maturity. The article also analyzes the works of Abdul Qadir Gilani, a major representative of Sufism.

Key words: occupation, personality, hard work, activity, halal food, lust, craft, social activity.

The essence of a person is material and spiritual being. Just as his spiritual existence should be nourished with knowledge, the concept of self lies in his material existence. That is, in order to satisfy the desire, man works, runs, and eats day and night. In order to satisfy these needs, people are divided into two categories: one is those who earn their livelihood by honest work, and the other is those who have made it their life principle to satisfy their material needs through various impure ways.

Abdul Qadir Gilani describes the ten qualities that lead to perfection and says that not being a burden to others brings the qualities of hard work and activity. And "Live your life not by your religion, but by your profession." Learn a trade and teach it to others. The profession of believers is the profession of sincerity. "There is a destiny only for those professions that ensure the use of the poor and the needy, show mercy to people and require the approval of Allah Almighty," says Abdul Qadir Gilani. He paid special attention to this issue in his work "Understanding Godliness and Gaining Merciful Grace". He emphasized that you should be busy with your profession, be busy with acquiring knowledge, and be busy with the implementation of your knowledge. But he said that it is necessary to carry out this occupation with foregah, that is, with sincerity, impartially, with the remembrance of Allah. Here, the negation of the negation is being created. If busyness negates idleness, laziness, and caring for someone else, busyness is denied by self-relaxation with God, and a beautiful moral virtue called "Relaxation with busyness" is born. Indeed, religion should not be a means of survival. After all, Islam condemns hypocrisy and arrogance. Making a living by profession is based on the motto of "work and relaxation" in the Qadiriya Tariqa. For this reason, Qadiriya was the most suitable road for the

people of Turkestan, whose people were farmers, gardeners, cattle breeders and craftsmen, and it was highly valued.

Meaning of busyness and relaxation:

- to be completely free from greed and selfishness;
- to be happy and proud that others are enjoying the material and spiritual wealth created by oneself;
- self-sacrifice for many people, and in return, it is to please the people of the world and expect a reward from God;

"Let him give to many, and let him give to me among many" is to work in prayer, "to be able to avoid the greed of one's ego";

- to live by appealing to one's conscience so that the gift that one wants to enjoy in the morning will not be lost.

This slogan was further developed by Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband as "Dast ba koru dil ba yor".

It is fair to say that halal food was typical for the people of Sufism. Representatives of the well-known and famous sects were famous for their profession, so their nicknames were added to the name of their profession. Among them, Abu Said Garroz Mahsidoz, Sheikh Khuja Abdullah Ansari, a shoemaker, Sheikh Muhammad Sakkok, a knife maker, Sheikh Abulfayz Haddad, a blacksmith, a shaykh who is considered the Qutb (the only saint of his time, Waliullah) and Ghawsi (helper) of his time. Abul Abbas Amili was a porter, Sheikh Abulhasan Najjar worked as a carpenter, Syed Amir was a potter by profession, Fariduddin Attar was an attar, and Hazrat Bahauddin were known as Naqshband because they were famous for "embroidering people".

The main criterion of this doctrine is that the heart should be occupied with hand-to-hand work with God, as hard work and work bring the name of a person to the top. This is the main essence of the doctrine of qadiriya, which continues its viability based on the motto "Engagement and relaxation".

So, being busy with work and hoping in God is the very essence of "Relaxing with Busyness".

There are also specific aspects of human maturity. For example, Professor Bakhtiyor Navroz-zoda analyzed its economic aspects in his scientific work. The following points of the scientist are noteworthy. Stages of the perfect human being from the point of view of economic usefulness:

At the first stage - man as labor force. This means an able-bodied, willing, physically healthy person.

The second stage is a person as a concrete labor subject. A person will have the ability to fully satisfy the needs of his family through his work. In other words, he is an economically perfect person.

The third stage is a person as an entrepreneur. In this case, the entrepreneur brings not only personal benefit, but also benefit to society from the products and benefits of his labor. Such people belong to the category of economically mature people.

The fourth stage is a person as a manager. At this stage, a person realizes his work and entrepreneurial skills in a corporate system. A corporation is the most developed organizational form of business, and its distinctive feature is the separation of management (managerial) tasks from the property owner. In order to increase the efficiency of business activities, the owner who established the corporation hires specialists with managerial qualities for the lower, middle and upper levels of management. In order to occupy managerial positions, a person must have the skills and experience of market management and receive management education. As a corporate manager, a person holds a managerial position in joint-stock companies on the basis of a contract and is engaged in business management activities. It ensures that the society works profitably. As a professional hired manager, he receives a salary for his work, and for the effective realization of his entrepreneurial abilities, the shareholder receives a certain percentage of the profits of the society. This share can amount to hundreds of thousands of soums per month. As a result, a person has the opportunity to have a happy marriage and achieve economic prosperity.

Thus, in the conditions of the market economy, a person is gradually: at first as a potential (labor force) and real (specific labor subject) personal factor of production, then as an entrepreneur engaged in small business activities of private entrepreneurship, and finally as a professional manager in the corporate system becomes economically mature.

We hope that the stages, levels and statuses of human maturity defined in the economic approach will serve as an important theoretical and methodological basis for educating an economically mature person during the transition to a market economy.

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